

Treatment in neonatology - A Fallow Land in Homœopathy

by Peter Mattmann-Allamand, Switzerland

In European countries 98% of deliveries happen in hospitals and the treatment of the early childhood (like that of pregnancy and delivery) is a wide fallow land in homœopathy. It is necessary to cultivate this land and to win back this territory of medicine. I believe the majority of handicaps is the result of an energetic damage and could be prevented by early homœopathic therapy. An Opium-child for example, who doesn't show any interest in his environment, isn't capable of a normal development. Its easier and cheaper to cure an *Opium* or *Cuprum*-state at this early age rather than to treat an adult person, who is handicapped or suffers from epileptic convulsions.

Homœopathic prescription in neonatology and early childhood is based on precise observation and perception of what is the normal behaviour and development.

Generally it is possible to make a sure prescription with a few clear symptoms. The signs and characteristics are directly visible and there isn't much room for speculation. In my opinion homœopathy in early childhood isn't more difficult than in adults.

A Case of *Asarum europaeum*

A new-born girl was strangled by the umbilical cord and had a blue asphyxia (delivery at home). After 10 min. mouth-to-mouth-resuscitation by the midwife respiration became spontaneous but accelerated. Hospitalisation for 2 days. On the 5th day the girl shows the following symptoms: open mouth and protruded tongue, snoring, red coloured face, small pupils, sleepiness between breast feeding. The mother says: "The child is not here, not present".

Opium C200 was prescribed which ameliorated in a few days. The girl was awake and the *Opium*-symptoms disappeared. But the girl was very easily frightened, especially by noises. This became more and more prominent and after 3 months the mother was a nervous wreck. After a slight noise (e.g. when the grandfather coughs slightly) or even without any reason the girl began to shriek endlessly. The girl stopped the shrieking only when the mother left the house and walked with her in the open air.

Rubrics :

Walking in open air amel. mental symptoms: (SR I, P.1061).

Sensitive to the slightest noise: (SRI, P.904).

Follow-up: 4 days after *Asarum* Q1 there was a dramatic amelioration, the mother said: The child is completely changed like a wonder. After an *Asarum* C200 a normal development took place. The child is today 21 months old. All neurological symptoms have disappeared.

A Case of *Cuprum metallicum*

Apart from a green amniotic fluid this boy had a normal birth (delivery at home). The midwife called me because the respiration-rate stayed pathologically high (90/min). The following symptoms were observed:

Quick movements (protruding) of the tongue, a very loud breathing noise (Ronchus neonatorum), a blue discoloration around the mouth, the fists were firmly closed, the thumbs clenched in, I could hardly open the fists, the toes were so cramped and contracted that it was impossible to clean between them, trembling chin, respiration accelerated, the child was frequently in a opisthotonos-position, twitching during the sleep.

Rubrics:

Face discoloration bluish about the mouth (RG P.302).

Extremities clenching fingers (RG P.802).

Extremities convulsion toes (RG P.812).

Back opisthotonus (RG P.752).

Respiration accelerated (RG P. 649).

Generalities twitching during sleep (RG. P.1162).

Mouth, protruded tongue, rapidly darting in and out like a snake's (RG. P.352).

Ronchus neonatorum (Imhäuser).

Follow-up:

After *Cuprum metallicum* C200 the symptoms were worse for 10 days, after

which they rapidly improved. After 3 months the examination was normal apart from a slight accelerated respiration and the twitching during sleep. The muscular tone and the development were completely normal. In my experience with homœopathy *Cuprum metallicum* is a polychrest in the early childhood. Nearly all my cases were connected with the green amniotic fluid, accelerated respiration and a general or partial muscular hypertonia.

A Case of *Opium*

I was called by a nurse-consultant and a midwife for a girl-baby (delivery in hospital), who was not able to drink from her mothers breast. They thought, that there must be a serious neurological problem or a buccal discoordination. The baby drank only two or three sips of milk, then stopped and fell asleep again.

The girl woke up only three times a day, at 8 hourly intervals and when she woke she didn't cry for feeding. The girl never cried at all. When I saw the two week old baby I made the following observations: A very marked general muscular hypotension, open mouth and half-open eyes during sleep. The girl was lying on the abdomen - completely unable to raise the head. On pulling her up into a sitting position the head fell back.

Rubrics:

Asks for nothing (SR I P.101)

Sleepiness overpowering (SR III P.114)

Head, unable to hold up the head (RG P.106)

Head falling backward while sitting (RG P.98)

Eye half open (RG P.208)

Mouth open during sleep (RG P.347)

Relaxation of muscles (SR II P.560) ➤

Reflexes diminished (SR II P.559)

Follow-up:

After *Opium* C200 the symptoms were aggravated for two weeks, after which there was a rapid amelioration. The girl became sensible to her own needs, she became hungry every 4 hours, the sleepiness disappeared. After 6 weeks there was still a slight general muscular hypotension. After 3 month the development was normal.

I have found *Opium* to be a polychrest in early childhood. In the majority of cases we find the state caused by a special fright. The older *Opium*-child is mentally paralysed by the fright: they don't cry or weep and they tell you nothing about the event. The key-note for the new-born *Opium*-child is "Non-presence". The mother says normally: "My child is not here, not present. There is something wrong".

A Case of *Theridion curassavicum*

This case is an example of how two characteristic symptoms were sufficient to find the right remedy. A 11 month old girl became ill just as the mother stopped nursing her. She developed a fever with changing paroxysms, apathy, lamenting and a terrible shrieking like a *crie encephalique*. Very often she would strain at stool and in these moments vomited. Frequently she touched her tongue as she would like to remove a hair from her tongue.

She was very pale. Perspiration was absent during the fever, the respiration was accelerated, she wanted to be carried all the time and was very thirsty. The examination of the urine showed a pyuria. The child had a severe inflammation of the urinary tract.

Rubrics:

Stomach, vomiting after straining for stool (RG P.455)

Mouth, hairy sensation in mouth (RGP.344)

Follow-up:

Two days after *Theridion* C30 she was much better and after two weeks the results from the urinary examination were normal.

References:

RG *Repertorium Generale*

SR *Synthetic Repertory*

Peter Mattmann-Allamand M.D.,
Taubenhausstrasse 10, CH-6005 Luzern
Peter Mattmann is a general practitioner and has practiced homœopathy for 10 years. His main focus is pregnancy care, Home birth and treatment of newborn and children.